

A Solution Based on Hub Selection and Robot Routing Optimization for Last-mile Delivery

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Abstract—This paper addresses the challenges in last-mile delivery by proposing an innovative solution employing Hub-and-Robots routing, strategically utilizing park-and-ride facilities as central hubs to optimize urban delivery operations. The increasing demand for rapid and efficient deliveries has necessitated a reevaluation of traditional delivery methodologies. The study focuses on optimizing last-mile delivery operations, minimizing the total distance of the routes traveled by robots, while satisfying customer requirements. Hub selection, leveraging existing infrastructure, and the potential use of park-and-ride facilities emerge as key considerations. The optimization model is applied to a case study involving two districts of the center of Bari (a city of Southern Italy) and a simulation validates the obtained results.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the dynamic logistics landscape, the last-mile delivery phase remains a critical challenge, particularly in the context of contemporary e-Commerce demands. To address the pressing need for efficient and timely deliveries, this paper explores a novel solution: Hub-and-Robot routing.

The realm of last-mile delivery optimization has garnered significant attention in the literature. It is an essential component to progress toward more sustainable cities, affecting diverse sectors of society, including tourism [12], commerce, and urban planning. Numerous studies have delved into this dynamic field, exploring various strategies to enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of delivering goods to end users.

Samouh et al., in [1] contribute to this discourse by proposing three distinct options for last-mile delivery: a robot delivery system, a drone delivery system, and a hybrid delivery system. Influencing last-mile deliveries positively, the utilization of robots results in enhanced delivery security and reduced delivery times [2].

In the research conducted by Heimfarth et al. [3], the authors offer a literature overview of various routing approaches related to robot-based deliveries. They identify

five delivery concepts: Truck-and-Drone delivery, delivery with cover options, Hub-and-Robot delivery, Truck-and-Robot without robot depots, and finally, Truck-and-Robot with robot depots.

In the investigation [4], Bakach et al. evaluate a two-tier last-mile delivery system utilizing robots, with a focus on optimizing the hubs and minimizing the travel distance of the robots. The authors suggest a system in which goods are transported by a truck to local hubs, where they are stored and loaded onto robots.

Studies [5] and [6], carried out by Poeting et al., explore similar concepts, focusing on efficient truck tours and robot scheduling for hub-based deliveries.

Since one of the most important points is customer satisfaction, research carried out by Jennings and Figliozzi [7] shows that autonomous robots can save time when traveling on sidewalks and, therefore, customers can get their product sooner than expected.

By integrating routing and last-mile delivery decisions, the research conducted by Alfandari et al. [14] improves service quality through the optimization of on-time deliveries, employing self-driving robots for the last-mile delivery process.

The use of autonomous robots for small deliveries over short distances, according to research carried out by Schaudt and Clausen [9], can reduce the number of late deliveries.

Chen et al. [10] have estimated that, with autonomous robots, customers could obtain their parcels quicker, there could be fewer vehicles on the roads, and delivery performance could be improved.

In [11], Sonneberg et al. propose a robot-only delivery system that is cost-optimal, showcasing cost reductions with additional robot compartments.

This paper focuses on the Hub-and-Robot approach, examining integrated routes to potentially avoid the need for specialized hubs and storage facilities. The proposed approach strategically combines centralized hubs, focusing on the use of park-and-ride facilities, and autonomous robots to enhance the speed, accuracy, and sustainability of last-mile deliveries. The selection of hubs plays a pivotal role in optimizing last-mile delivery systems, particularly when incorporating autonomous robots into the logistic framework. Choosing existing infrastructure as the base for these hubs is crucial for several reasons.

Firstly, an already established infrastructure ensures a more cost-effective and sustainable implementation.

Secondly, the strategic choice of hubs for last-mile delivery in a city is a decision that involves considerations such as proximity to high-demand areas, traffic patterns, and

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accessibility. Optimal placement of the hub can significantly reduce the overall distance traveled by robots, contributing to the efficiency and expediency of the entire last-mile delivery process.

The advantage of park-and-ride facilities lies in their established infrastructure, often equipped with parking spaces, central locations, and accessibility. Purposing these facilities for last-mile delivery operations with autonomous robots can offer a dual benefit: minimizing the need for additional construction while strategically situating hubs in key areas. Their proximity to high-demand areas, coupled with convenient access points, can significantly optimize the overall efficiency of last-mile deliveries.

This paper explores how optimizing last-mile delivery through the Hub-and-Robot approach that can play a crucial role in fostering sustainability. To this aim a Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP) problem is formulated with the objective of minimizing the total length of the routes traveled by robots while satisfying customer requirements.

The model is applied to a case study describing the last mile delivery problem in two districts of the city of Bari (Italy). The results shows the efficiency in the distribution of goods and services to locations.

Moreover, to validate the optimization results in a more realist framework, the obtained solutions are implemented in a simulation environment. The simulation results show the impact of the traffic in the travel times of the robots and the relativ delivery operations.

The innovation of this paper stands out by strategically placing the hubs in park-and-ride facilities, leveraging the advantages of this location, such as proximity to high-demand areas, central accessibility, and existing infrastructure.

The paper is organized as follows. Section II presents the description of the problem, in which the mathematical model is presented. Moreover, Section III delves into the case study and describes the results obtained by applying the optimization model and the simulation. Finally, Section IV concludes the article, summarizing the main findings and implications.

II. PROBLEM DESCRIPTION

This section details the proposed last-mile delivery system, incorporating the Hub-and-Robot routing approach. In our problem scenario, as shown in Figure 1, a truck serves as the primary transporter for goods and robots, transporting them to the hub. It is at the hub where the robots loads parcels and subsequently deliver them to the designated customers.

The proposed study focuses on figuring out the best routes for a group of robots that need to deliver parcels to specific customers, taking into account cargo capacity and time limits.

The robots under consideration in this problem are equipped with batteries capable of providing up to 40 km of autonomy, with no consideration given to the real-time battery charge status. In this scenario, the main objective is to minimize the total length of the robots traveled routes.

Fig. 1. Last-Mile Hub-and-Robot Delivery flow

The operational sequence begins with the robots departing from the central hub to deliver parcels to customers. Respecting the predefined time constraints, the robots then return to the hub, strategically picking up additional parcels for subsequent deliveries. This cyclical process ensures an efficient and continuous operation, as the robots seamlessly shuttle between the central hub and designated customer locations. The optimization of this dynamic workflow lies at the core of our proposed last-mile delivery strategy.

A mathematical model has been created in order to solve the routing problem. This model considers different factors, such as how much each robot can carry, the time limits, and the total distance they travel. By using this optimization model, our goal is to make last-mile delivery faster and improve how things work in city logistics.

A. Optimization model

The main objective of the last-mile delivery with robots is the distribution of parcels from the hub, located in a park-and-ride, to the customer nodes.

To visualize and organize the delivery flow, the entire network has been modeled using a fully connected directed graph, denoted G . This graph covers both the hubs \mathcal{H} and the customer nodes \mathcal{N}' , representing the complete delivery network.

Customer demands d_i are quantified in terms of unit parcels, with no consideration given to the weight of the packages. Furthermore, the delivery service time s_i is measured in minutes, reflecting the time taken to complete each delivery successfully.

The weight of the arcs \mathcal{A} connecting the nodes \mathcal{N} is assigned as the distance in kilometers [13] between each pair of nodes. Additionally, the travel time between nodes is calculated based on the average speed considered for the robot.

To carry out the deliveries, the system employs several routes, denoted as m , wherein each robot, denoted as r and belonging to the set \mathcal{R} , initiates its journey from and concludes it at the hub.

The optimization model relies on the following parameters and decision variables, each contributing to the efficiency

and effectiveness of the last-mile delivery system:

Parameters and decisional variables

\mathcal{A}	Set of arcs with $A = \mathcal{A} $ and $ (.) $ stands for cardinality of the set $(.)$
\mathcal{R}	Set of robots with $R = \mathcal{R} $
\mathcal{N}'	Set of Customers with $N' = \mathcal{N}' $
\mathcal{N}	Set of Nodes with $N = \mathcal{N} $
\mathcal{H}	Set of hubs with $H = \mathcal{H} $
y_h^r	Binary parameter that indicates if robot $r \in \mathcal{R}$ belongs to hub $h \in \mathcal{H}$
d_i	Demand of customer $n_i \in \mathcal{N}'$ [unit parcels]
s_i	Service duration at customer $n_i \in \mathcal{N}'$ [minutes]
$open_i$	Opening service hour at customer $n_i \in \mathcal{N}'$ [h]
$close_i$	Closing service hour at the customer $n_i \in \mathcal{N}'$ [h]
P^r	Cargo capacity of robot $r \in \mathcal{R}$ [unit parcels]
W_i^r	Starting time of the delivery of robot $r \in \mathcal{R}$ at node $n_i \in \mathcal{N}'$ [minutes]
W^r	Working time of robots $r \in \mathcal{R}$ [minutes]
m	Route index of each robot trip
$td_{i,j}$	Distance to travel from n_i to n_j . $n_i, n_j \in \mathcal{N}$ [km]
$tt_{i,j}$	Time to travel from n_i to n_j . $n_i, n_j \in \mathcal{N}$ [minutes]
T_r	Maximum working time of each robot $r \in \mathcal{R}$ [minutes]
$L_{i,m}^r$	Total cargo load of robot $r \in \mathcal{R}$ at node $n_i \in \mathcal{N}$ during the route m
$x_{i,j}^r$	Binary decision variable equal to 1 if robot $r \in \mathcal{R}$ travels from node $n_i \in \mathcal{N}$ to node $n_j \in \mathcal{N}$

The mathematical model is formulated as a MILP. Note that, to simplify the formulation layout, the time dependence (t) is omitted in the following formulation.

$$\min \sum_{r=1}^{\mathcal{R}} \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{i,j:a_{ij} \in \mathcal{A}} td_{i,j} \cdot x_{i,j,m}^r \quad (1)$$

Subject to:

$$\sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{r=1}^{\mathcal{R}} \sum_{i,j:a_{ij} \in \mathcal{A}} x_{i,j,m}^r = 1 \quad (2)$$

$$\forall n_i \in \mathcal{N}'$$

$$\sum_{j:a_{h,j} \in \mathcal{A}} x_{h,j,m}^r \cdot y_h^r = 1 \quad (3)$$

$$\forall r \in \mathcal{R}, \forall h \in \mathcal{H}, \forall m$$

$$\sum_{j:a_{i,h} \in \mathcal{A}} x_{i,h,m}^r \cdot y_h^r \leq 1 \quad (4)$$

$$\forall r \in \mathcal{R}, m = 1, \dots, M, \forall h \in \mathcal{H}$$

$$\sum_{i:a_{i,j} \in \mathcal{A}} x_{i,j,m}^r \cdot y_h^r - \sum_{i:a_{i,j} \in \mathcal{A}-a_{j,h}} x_{j,i,m}^r \cdot y_h^r = 0 \quad (5)$$

$$\forall r \in \mathcal{R}, \forall n_j \in \mathcal{N}', \forall m, \forall h \in \mathcal{H}$$

$$\sum_{i:a_{i,h} \in \mathcal{A}} x_{i,h,m}^r \cdot y_h^r - \sum_{i:a_{h,j} \in \mathcal{A}} x_{h,j,m+1}^r \cdot y_h^r = 0 \quad (6)$$

$$\forall r \in \mathcal{R}, \forall m = 1, 2, \dots, M-1, \forall h \in \mathcal{H}$$

$$W_{j,m}^r \geq W_{i,m}^r + s_i + tt_{i,j} \quad (7)$$

$$x_{i,j}^r = 1, \forall r \in \mathcal{R}, \forall a_{i,j} \in \mathcal{A}, \forall m$$

$$L_{j,m}^r = L_{i,m}^r + d_j \quad (8)$$

$$x_{h,j,m}^r = 1, \forall r \in \mathcal{R}, \forall h \in \mathcal{H}$$

$$\forall a_{i,j} \in \mathcal{A}, s.t. i \neq h, \forall m$$

$$L_{j,m}^r = d_j \quad (9)$$

$$x_{h,j,m}^r = 1, \forall r \in \mathcal{R}, \forall h \in \mathcal{H}$$

$$\forall j.s.t. a_{h,j} \in \mathcal{A}, \forall m > 1$$

$$open_{i,m} \leq W_{i,m}^r \leq close_{i,m} \quad (10)$$

$$\forall r \in \mathcal{R}, \forall m, \forall n_i \in \mathcal{N}'$$

$$0 \leq W^r \leq T_r \quad (11)$$

$$\forall r \in \mathcal{R}, \forall m$$

$$0 \leq L_{i,m}^r \leq P^r \quad (12)$$

$$\forall r \in \mathcal{R}, \forall n_i \in \mathcal{N}, \forall m$$

$$x_{i,j,m}^r \in \{0, 1\} \quad (13)$$

The primary goal of the objective function (1) is to minimize the total length of the routes traveled by robots $r \in \mathcal{R}$ while satisfying customer requirements.

To ensure that each customer node is served only once, constraints (2) are enforced.

Constraints (3) dictate that each robot $r \in \mathcal{R}$ departs from hub $h \in \mathcal{H}$ in all routes m . For every robot $r \in \mathcal{R}$, constraints (4) determine that the route m concludes at hub $h \in \mathcal{H}$.

Constraints (5) guarantee the conservation of flow, while constraints (6) establish a connection between the end of route m and the start of route $m+1$.

Arrival time at node n_j is modeled by constraints (7), which involve summing up the arrival time at node n_i , the delivery operation time s_i at node n_i , and the travel time of robot $r \in \mathcal{R}$ through the arc $a_{i,j} \in \mathcal{A}$.

Constraints (8) and (9) are responsible for updating the cargo load $L_{i,m}^r$ of each robot $r \in \mathcal{R}$.

Constraints (10) ensures that delivery made by robot $r \in \mathcal{R}$ takes place within the time limit established by customer

$n_i \in \mathcal{N}'$. Constraints (11) and (12) define the working time and cargo capacity bounds for each robot $r \in \mathcal{R}$.

Finally, constraints (13) define the binary decision variable $x_{i,j,m}^r$.

III. CASE STUDY

A. System Description

The case study focuses on two districts of the city of Bari, located in southern Italy: Murat and Madonella. In each neighborhood, 12 customers are considered.

Facilitating delivery operations are two strategically positioned hubs, one for each neighborhood. These hubs are strategically located within the park-and-ride facilities, exploiting the advantages of the location: proximity to high-demand areas, central accessibility, existing infrastructure.

The hubs serve as central command centers coordinating the activities of an autonomous fleet comprising 8 robots. Each hub is equipped with 4 robots, as detailed in Table I, specifying crucial parameters such as departure hub, medium speed, maximum working time, and cargo capacity for each robot.

TABLE I
ROBOTS DATA

Robot	Departure hub	Medium speed [km/h]	T_w [min]	P^r [parcel units]
$r_1 - r_4$	HUB 1	6.5	540	2
$r_5 - r_8$	HUB 2	6.5	540	2

The primary objective of the case study is to optimize the route planning for robots, ensuring the most efficient delivery of parcels to the 12 clients in each neighborhood. The objective is to minimize the distance traveled, consequently reducing the overall delivery time. Figure 2 shows the last-mile delivery network in the city of Bari including customers locations and hub positions.

Fig. 2. Last-Mile Delivery Network

As detailed in Table II, nodes from n_0 to n_{11} correspond to Murat neighborhood, while nodes from n_{12} to n_{23} pertain to Madonella neighborhood. HUB1 is identified as n_{24} , and HUB2 is designated as n_{25} . The service duration at each customer is considered to be 10 minutes.

TABLE II
NODES DATA

Zone	n_i	s_i [min]	$open_i$ [h]	$close_i$ [h]
Murat	$n_0 - n_{11}$	10	8:00	17:00
Madonella	$n_{12} - n_{23}$	10	8:00	17:00
HUB 1	n_{24}	10	-	-
HUB 2	n_{25}	10	-	-

The nodes closest to HUB1 are n_{22} and n_{23} , while the farthest nodes are n_0 and n_1 . Conversely, in the case of HUB2, the closest nodes are n_0 and n_1 , and the farthest nodes are n_{22} and n_{23} .

B. Optimization Results

This section presents the results of optimizing the last-mile delivery with the Hub-and-Robot delivery problem. The model has been implemented by Cplex with a CPU 12th Gen Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-12700K, 3600 Mhz and a RAM of 16GB and the solution is found in few minutes.

Table III illustrates the distinct routes executed by each robot in the fleet. It is evident that all 24 customers have been successfully served, and interestingly, not all robots have been utilized, showcasing an efficient allocation of resources. Only 2 robots departing from HUB1 and 2 robots departing from HUB2 have been utilized in the current scenario.

TABLE III
ROBOTS ROUTES

Robot	Starting hub	Customers served n_i
r_1	HUB 1	3 - 2
		23 - 22
		19 - 18
		21 - 20
r_2	HUB 1	8 - 6
		17 - 14
		15 - 13
		16
r_5	HUB 2	11 - 10
		1 - 4
		5 - 9
		12 - 0
r_6	HUB 2	7

It can be observed that each robot executes a maximum of 4 routes, delivering to 2 customers in each route, representing the maximum capacity. However, exceptions to this pattern are found in the last route of robot r_2 and that of robot r_6 , where a different configuration is employed.

TABLE IV
ROBOTS TIME AND DISTANCE RESULTS

ROBOT	Departure time [h:mm]	Travel time [min]	Travel distance [km]
r_1	9:13	203.07	13.55
r_2	9:14	214.35	15.83
r_5	8:54	198.71	13.07
r_6	8:38	37.63	3.02

As shown in Table IV, all robots, encompassing both those departing from HUB1 and HUB2, have collectively covered a total distance of 45 km.

Furthermore, the analysis reveals that the entire allocated time of 540 minutes has not been fully utilized, indicating a streamlined and expedient last-mile delivery process.

C. Simulation Results

To check the solutions reported in Section III.A in slightly realistic conditions, we simulate the case study in SUMO simulation software. SUMO program is designed for building, researching, and optimizing virtual models of physical and technical objects [14]. The pedestrian roads of each zone are reported from Google Maps to SUMO.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This paper introduces an Hub-and-Robots routing approach to optimize last-mile delivery in urban settings. By strategically deploying centralized hubs and leveraging autonomous robots, the study focuses on minimizing travel distances and, consequently, reducing overall delivery times.

The system is modeled by a Mixed Integer Linear Programming problem that minimizes the total length of the robot routes by satisfying the customer requirements.

The results obtained in a case study developed for the city of Bari (Italy) demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed solution in successfully serving all customers within the allocated time, showcasing efficient resource allocation. A simulation study allows validating the obtained results in a more realistic framework where traffic is also considered.

Further research will be twofold. First, a systematic technique will be proposed for the hub positioning in the cities. Second, a heuristic algorithm will be developed to enhance the scalability and adaptability of the proposed optimization model.

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